

PREPREG STYLE FABRICATION OF ALL-CELLULOSE COMPOSITES

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Abstract

Increased environmental awareness and the demand for improved sustainability and biodegradability has led to increased interest in naturally derived materials. All-cellulose composites (ACCs) represent one group of green, bio-compostable composites with the potential to overcome our dependence on non-renewable polymers. Research on ACCs to date have demonstrated the excellent potential mechanical properties achievable, however, the majority of these studies are largely fundamental in nature. The work outlined here aims to redress this by demonstrating the possibility of adapting an existing manufacturing technique to produce larger and thicker ACCs. Solutions of various celluloses pre-dissolved in the ionic liquid (IL) 1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium acetate (EmimAc) were used to impregnate cellulose textiles using a roller system. Storage of the impregnated layers allowed a limited amount of moisture to solidify the dissolved cellulose resulting in prepreg style ACC laminate layers. These ACC prepreps were then consolidated into a multi-laminate ACC using hot pressing at 120°C. The IL was washed out using distilled water and the ACC laminate was dried resulting in a final composite 100 by 100 mm with a thickness of around 2 mm. Analysis showed void reduction with increasing processing time, with samples processed for 4 hrs showing significant improvements over the 1 and 2 hr samples. Mechanical testing revealed tensile strengths of around 100 MPa for all ACCs. Young's modulus and flexural properties increased as void content was reduced, whereas elongation to failure values reduced. The laminates produced had high fibre volume fractions in excess of 80%. The effect of different matrix celluloses had a limited effect, partially due to the void content and in part due to

the low matrix volume in the composite. The procedure developed allows for the up-scaled manufacture of ACCs with good mechanical properties based on a currently widespread composite processing style.

1 Introduction

The combination of high mechanical properties, widespread availability, biodegradability and sustainability has generated much interest in cellulose as a potential replacement for existing petro-chemically derived polymers [1,2]. Cellulose is made up of a complex network of glucose units interconnected by hydrogen bonds. Glucose units are linked at the C₁ and C₄ positions, and two glucose units rotated at 180° to each other are linked to form cellobiose. Linear molecules of cellobiose are coupled to form cellulose chains [3]. The length of the chain depends on the number of glucose units, referred to as degree of polymerization (DP) [4]. The source of the cellulose largely determines the degree of polymerization. Native cellulose has a very high DP, ranging to well in excess of 10000 in cellulose sources such as cotton and linen [5,6,7]. However, the DP can decrease by 40% with dissolution processing, in some cases reducing the potential strength of cellulose composites [8]. Intrinsically, cellulose has excellent mechanical properties, providing the structural support in plants [9]. As such, strength and stiffness values for cellulose I or native cellulose have been reported to be as high as 13-17 GPa and 130 GPa, respectively [10,11,12].

These excellent potential mechanical properties have induced substantial research in the area of biocomposites with the aim of transferring these properties to replace petro-chemically derived materials [13]. Cellulosic fibres have to date been

widely used as reinforcement for polymers, although chemical incompatibility between the hydrophobic polymer matrix and hydrophilic cellulose has led to difficulties in fully exploiting the mechanical properties of cellulosic fibres. Despite improvements in fibre-matrix adhesion *via* a variety of chemical and physical methods, issues still remain in terms of the optimization of mechanical properties, rise in production cost and biodegradability of modified cellulose fibres [13,14,15].

Recently, the concept of single-polymer composites has been explored to allow fabrication of pure cellulose composites. All-cellulose composites (ACCs) are hypothesized to overcome the fibre-matrix incompatibility issues as both the matrix and reinforcement phases are chemically similar [16]. ACCs can still be termed composites as the fibre and matrix may be different polymorphs of cellulose and/or exhibit differences in crystallinity. Processing of ACCs involves either partially dissolving cellulose fibres in a solvent to form the matrix phase *in situ* [17] or fully dissolving cellulose in a solvent and then adding cellulose-based reinforcement fibres [18]. Research in the ACC field has demonstrated desirable mechanical properties with tensile strengths reported to be as high as 400-500 MPa and an elastic modulus of 18 GPa for bi-axial composites [16]. Most studies of ACCs in the literature to date have focussed on producing single layer, lab-scale composites [19]. Recently, Huber *et al.* developed an up-scaled manufacturing process termed solvent infusion processing (SIP) that is conceptually based on vacuum-assisted resin transfer moulding. SIP of ACCs is based on the partial dissolution principle using cellulose fibre textiles. The ACCs produced *via* SIP have a reported strength and modulus of 100 MPa and 5 GPa, respectively [20].

The synthesis of ACCs requires solvents capable of interrupting the strong inter- and intra-molecular hydrogen bonding within cellulose crystallites. Some ionic liquids (ILs) such as 1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium acetate (EmimAc) are highly efficient solvents for cellulose, capable of dissolving around 20 wt. % [21,22,23,24]. Viscosity plays a major role in the dissolution of cellulose, with an increase in temperature reducing the viscosity and increasing dissolution capability, with temperatures between 80 and 130°C accounting for the vast majority of cellulose dissolution studies [3]. The

interaction between cellulose and IL is disrupted during regeneration by the addition of a coagulant such as water, acetone or ethanol. ILs are largely recyclable due to their low volatility, making ILs clean and environmentally friendly solvents [25,26].

The focus of the present research is to develop an industrially-orientated processing route for ACC laminates that is based on a prepreg approach. Pre-impregnated textiles (or prepreps) are extensively used in the manufacture of traditional composite laminates for increasing the production rate and quality of the final composites [27]. This processing route allows for high quality composites to be produced with high fibre volume fractions by negating the need for hand impregnation of the textiles. The effect of the DP of the dissolved cellulose matrix material and its effect on the properties on the final composite are also investigated.

2 Materials and Method

2.1 Preparation of precursors

Cellulose powders (Sigmacell Type 20, Sigma-Aldrich, St. Louis, USA, DP~200; and Arbocel BC 200, J. Rettenmaier & Söhne GmbH, Rosenberg, Germany; DP~1500) and pulp (Cordenka GmbH, Obernburg, Germany; DP~800) were each fully dissolved in 1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium acetate (EmimAc, Sigma-Aldrich) at 100°C. 10% cellulose by weight was added to the IL for each of the celluloses. Dissolved Sigmacell, pulp and Arbocel matrix materials are denoted as S, P and A, respectively. Rayon fibres (Cordenka GmbH) were prepared as a woven textile (K2/2) with an areal weight of 450 gm⁻². The matrix materials and textile were dried at 100°C under vacuum prior to use.

2.2 Prepreg processing

The rayon textiles were impregnated with the various cellulose solutions (S, P and A) using a pair of rollers (Fig. 1). These layers were then stored for 24 hrs under ambient conditions in a sealed container. The mass of the pre-impregnated laminae was measured before and after storage.

2.3 Preparation of ACC laminates

4 of the prepreg laminae were hot pressed at 120°C under vacuum for times of 60, 120 and 240 min using a pressure of 2 MPa (Fig. 1). Samples are designated by matrix type and processing time (*e.g.* S60 indicates a sample based on a Sigmacell matrix and processed for 1 hr). The hot-pressed consolidated ACCs were then placed in distilled water to regenerate the dissolved cellulose. Water was changed until the IL had been completely removed from the laminate. Subsequently, the regenerated laminae were dried under vacuum at 60°C and 500 kPa. The ACC laminates were finally conditioned at 23°C and R.H. of 50% for 48 hrs before analysis.

2.4 Materials characterisation

The microstructure and fracture surfaces of the ACC laminates were observed by optical (Leica DM IRM (Wetzlar, Germany) and scanning electron (JEOL 7000F SEM, Tokyo, Japan) microscopy. Micrographs were analysed using Gimp 2.8.2 image analysis software to determine the fibre volume fraction and void content.

Tensile and flexural testing was also used to characterize the mechanical properties of the ACC laminates. Samples were cut into coupons of 5-8 mm width and 100 mm length for tensile testing and 12.5 mm width and 60 mm length for flexural testing. The samples were tested with an MTS 858 Tabletop System tensile tester or MTS Criterion Model 43 tensile tester equipped with a video extensometer, using a 2.5 kN load cell. A 3-point bending fixture with a span of 40 mm was used to analyze the flexural strength. Tensile tests were performed at a test rate of 1 mm/min and flexural testing was conducted at 2 mm/min.

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Effect of moisture uptake on prepreg storage

EmimAc is known to be a highly hydrophilic IL, capable of absorbing moisture mass in excess of 100% from the atmosphere [29]. It was observed that moisture absorbed by the IL during exposure to ambient conditions partially regenerated the cellulose. The net effect of this was to ensure that the IL was not lost during storage of the prepreg. 0.5 wt. % of moisture was absorbed by the prepregs which was sufficient to help “solidify” the laminae.

3.2 Effect of processing on microstructure

The use of rollers allowed for repeatable and consistent impregnation of the reinforcement textile. 4 layers of prepreg resulted in an ACC laminate of 1.8 to 2 mm in thickness, following regeneration and drying. The average mass of textile reinforcement was 1.25 times that of the impregnating solution with deviations of 10% across all composites produced, implying that the roller impregnation method is reliable, accurate and repeatable. Despite the high areal density of the reinforcement textile, it was still possible to fully impregnate the fibre yarns with the solutions (Fig. 2). The fibre volume fraction

Fig. 1. ACC prepreg fabrication method.

(FVF) in the ACC laminates was in the region of 80% for all samples (Table 1). A high FVF was expected since only 10% of cellulose is contained in the matrix solution, so once the IL is removed only the initial dissolved cellulose and partially dissolved reinforcement cellulose remain.

Fig. 2. Impregnated A60 ACC prepreg.

Table 1. Average values and standard deviation of the FVF of various ACC laminates.

Sample	S		P		A	
	Avg %	Dev %	Avg %	Dev %	Avg %	Dev %
240	79.46	1.99	80.66	2.23	82.17	4.04
120	81.28	3.42	79.47	5.43	79.12	3.68
60	78.99	1.94	80.49	3.24	79.8	3.4

Presumably, a longer processing time will dissolve more of the reinforcement fibres and therefore reduce FVF. Table 1 indicates that this is not true, the reason being that the moisture contained in the solution must be removed before dissolution will commence. The processing time of 1 h is too brief and causes numerous large voids and cracks to form within the laminate, reducing the mechanical properties (see Figs. 5 and 8). As the IL is heated, it slowly releases the moisture absorbed during storage and then begins to dissolve the reinforcement material. Partial dissolution can be seen to occur gradually from the outside of the fibre bundle, slowly progressing towards the centre over time. The elevated temperature allows for further cellulose dissolution to take place, causing the reinforcement fibres to partially dissolve and become part of the matrix (Fig. 3). This also explains the reason for the

slight decrease in fibre volume fraction of the prepreg S240 when compared to S120.

Drying of the composite plays a major role in crack formation. After solvent exchange, both fibres and matrix phases have swollen due to the presence of water [31,32]. As this water is removed by the elevated temperature and pressure, the composite will start to contract. The transition area between fully impregnated but non-partially dissolved region and the partially dissolved region induces voids and cracks where the pre-dissolved cellulose and reinforcement cellulose contract or shrink at different rates, labelled in Fig. 4 as region A and B, respectively. Partially, some of the voids are formed after processing during the regeneration phase. Different cellulose types contain different crystallinities and therefore react, absorb and release moisture differently, causing inhomogeneties in the composite [33]. This causes the matrix material to shrink slightly differently and causes small voids between the fibre and the matrix material, as shown by region A in Fig. 4 and in Fig. 2. If the solution begins to dissolve the fibres, the cellulose matrix and fibres are more similar as some of the fibre is contained in the matrix. This in turn causes the fibres and matrix to shrink at a more similar rate and reduces the possibility of the matrix breaking away from the fibre (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. Partial dissolution of reinforcement fibres in ACC prepreg S120 (an area of extensive fibre matrix transition is circled).

Increasing the processing time from 1 to 4 h reduces the void content by providing more time for matrix

and reinforcement fibres to bond. Crack and void content in the composites was determined and showed a reduction in defects with increasing processing time (Table 2). Initial defect content in the 1 hour samples was quite high at around 10%. This inevitably has a major effect on the mechanical properties, especially regarding the stiffness and flexural properties of the composites [34].

Fig. 4. Crack formation in prepreg A60 due to transition between (A) non-partially dissolved region and (B) partially dissolved region.

Table 2. Average values and standard deviation of the void content in prepreg ACCs.

Sample	S		P		A	
	Avg %	Dev %	Avg %	Dev %	Avg %	Dev %
240	7.61	1.2	7.76	1.69	6.69	4.04
120	7.98	2.59	8.12	1.6	8.04	4.28
60	10.17	2.37	9.52	1.71	8.9	2.58

3.3 Tensile properties

Tensile strengths for all ACC laminates produced were approximately 100 MPa (Fig. 5), comparing favorably to other biocomposites and similar to other ACC laminates [16,20]. Void formation had a major impact on the Young’s modulus of the ACCs, resulting in stiffness values lower than that of ACCs produced using alternative processes [20] but still competitive with other biocomposites based on polylactic acid (PLA) [16,35]. The void content tended to decrease with increasing processing time, resulting in an increased stiffness. Void content has been well documented to significantly reduce

material properties of composite materials [34,36]. Composites processed for 4 hrs had twice the stiffness of the composites processed for 1 hr, increasing from around 1 to over 2 GPa (Fig 5). This indicates that a substantial amount of time is required to remove the moisture from the matrix and allow bonding of the matrix and fibres. Interestingly, the type of matrix cellulose used seems to have very little effect on the final composite properties, with void content dominating the stiffness behavior of the material (Fig 5). Another reason for this negligible variation in matrix stiffness is the low volume of actual matrix. The matrix content in the prepreg ACCs is just over 10%. Due to the small matrix content, the effects of different matrix celluloses will be limited. The only exception to this is the S120 sample which due to the lower DP of the dissolved Sigmacell means the impregnating solution has a lower viscosity [37]. This reduced viscosity enables partial dissolution of the reinforcement fibres sooner than the Arbocel and pulp matrix solutions [3]. For a 2 hr processing time, it is therefore possible for the Sigmacell solution to provide stronger adherence between fibres and matrix which translates into improved stiffness values in the composite.

1 hr composites showed significantly higher elongation at break properties in the region of 30% compared to ACCs processed for longer (around 20% elongation). As previously discussed, fibre matrix adhesion increases with processing time, so 1 hr ACCs showed significant fibre pull-out when compared to 2 or 4 hr samples. In the 1 hour samples, the matrix and well bonded region breaks but subsequently all the load is taken by the fibres (Fig 6) which also have excellent elongation properties [38,39]. Better bonded composites showed elongation to failure values of around 20%. These composites also showed much less fibres being pulled away from the matrix, resulting instead in fibre failure in the composite (Fig 7).

Fig. 5. Tensile properties of ACC prepregs.

Fig. 6. Tensile fracture of S60 showing (A) fibre pull-out in poorly bonded regions and (B) fibre failure in well consolidated region.

Fig. 7. Tensile fracture of S120, showing extensive fibre failure.

3.4 Flexural properties

Initial flexural properties of the 60 min samples were lower than anticipated. Flexural testing on ACCs produced by the partial dissolution method showed flexural strengths of 140 MPa [40]. This was primarily due to the large number of voids and cracks and poor interfacial bonding between the fibres and the matrix phases. Studies by Liu *et al.* and de Almeida *et al.* showed that a slight increase in void content has a major negative impact on flexural properties of composites [34,36]. Increased processing time reduced these defects and improved bonding allowing for an increase in flexural strength and stiffness values. 2 hour samples only showed minimal improvement, whereas 4 hour samples improved flexural strength by around 50% and flexural stiffness values almost doubled (Fig 8). As with the tensile test samples no trends could be established for different cellulose matrix materials, with again only S120 showing increased flexural stiffness when compared with A120 and P120. The reason for this slight increase is the same as outlined in section 3.3. No significant difference could be observed for the flexural properties using different matrix celluloses, which is again due to the low matrix content of the prepreg ACCs, with the matrix content being too low to significantly impact the flexural properties. However, a reduction in void content produces an immediate and significant increase in flexural strength and stiffness [34]. The

reduction of voids has the effect of limiting shear within the material during bending [36]. More complete fibre-matrix bonding in the 4 hr ACC prepregs as a result of longer processing allows for better bonding reducing void content and increasing flexural strength and stiffness (Fig. 8).

Fig. 8. Flexural properties of ACC prepregs.

4 Conclusions

The developed procedure allowed for repeatable fabrication of all-cellulose composites. This industrially orientated processing route incorporates an existing composite fabrication technology and demonstrates the ability of all-cellulose composites to be manufactured in a prepreg style process. The application of heat and pressure during processing first releases the absorbed moisture and then bonds the individual layers to produce ACC laminates. Mechanical testing revealed excellent mechanical strength and elongation properties, while increased processing time improved composite stiffness. Similarly, flexural properties also increased with processing time. Interestingly, the choice of cellulose reinforcement cellulose did not appear to strongly influence the mechanical properties, despite large variations in DP. Presumably, the matrix does not dominate the mechanical properties since it is present as a low volume fraction of the final ACC

laminates. Void content proved to be the governing factor for both composite stiffness and flexural properties. Due to the extremely hydrophilic nature of the IL used, extended processing times at elevated temperatures were required to allow the absorbed moisture to escape from the composite.

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